

Stability Constants of 2-Hydroxy-1-Naphthaldehyde-Thiosemicarbazone Complexes with some Bivalent Metal Ions

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Stability constants of complexes of some bivalent metals viz., Cu^{++} , Ni^{++} , Co^{++} , Zn^{++} , Cd^{++} and Mg^{++} with 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde-thiosemicarbazone have been determined potentiometrically in 75 per cent dioxan and 0.1M sodium perchlorate medium. The order of the stability constants for the complexes is found to be $\text{Cu} > \text{Co} > \text{Ni} > \text{Zn} > \text{Cd} > \text{Mg}$.

RUSINA and Sirota¹ have studied the colour of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde-thiosemicarbazone in the alkaline range by spectrophotometric method. They have also determined the value of the dissociation constant of the 'OH' group in the ortho position by the potentiometric method at 20° in 40 per cent (vol) acetone. However, no systematic study of the stabilities of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde-thiosemicarbazone and its metal chelates with bivalent metal ions appears to have been carried out.

In the present communication the successive stability constants of the complexes of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde-thiosemicarbazone with various bivalent metal ions have been determined potentiometrically following the Calvin-Bjerrum pH titration technique as adopted by Irving and Rossotti.²

Experimental

The Corning Model 12, a precision research pH meter with a wide range glass electrode and a calomel reference electrode was used for pH measurements. The meter has an arrangement for normal and expanded scale. The smallest scale division on the expanded scale is 0.005 pH unit.

The ligand 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde-thiosemicarbazone was synthesised and crystallised to get an analytically pure sample (m.p. 276°).³

All the chemicals used except the ligand and perchloric acid were of B.D.H. analytical grade. The perchloric acid used was of E. Merck G.R. grade.

The medium of titration was dioxan-water mixture containing 75 per cent (v/v) of dioxan. The dioxan used for the experiments was purified by the method described by Vogel.⁴ Distilled water, redistilled over alkaline potassium permanganate and made free from carbon dioxide by boiling, was used throughout the investigation. Sodium perchlorate was added to maintain a constant ionic strength (0.1M). The titrations were carried out in an inert atmosphere by bubbling the nitrogen gas through the solutions. All the metal perchlorate solutions were standardised

complexometrically⁵ by E.D.T.A. titrations. All measurements were made at $30^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$.

The following solutions were titrated potentiometrically against standard carbonate-free sodium hydroxide (1.092M) solution, keeping the total volume 40 ml.

- (i) 5 ml of 0.16M HClO_4 + 5 ml of 0.64M NaClO_4 + 30 ml of dioxan.
- (ii) 5 ml of 0.16M HClO_4 + 5 ml of 0.64M NaClO_4 + requisite amount of reagent accurately weighed to give 0.01M reagent concentration in the final solution + 30 ml of dioxan.
- (iii) 5 ml of NaClO_4 + 5 ml of metal salt (0.024M) solution in 0.16M HClO_4 + requisite amount of the reagent accurately weighed to give 0.01 ligand concentration in the final solution.

The experimental method of Irving and Rossotti² was applied to find out the values of \bar{n} and pL.

Results and Discussions

In the ligand, it is the chelated phenolic 'OH' group which takes part in the complex formation and the proton is replaced from it by metal ions during the formation of metal chelate. Since only one proton per ligand molecule is liberated during complexation, 'y', the number of the dissociable protons attached per ligand molecule is equal to one.

From the titration curves using the solutions (i) and (ii), \bar{n}_A values at various B values (pH meter readings) were calculated, and the curve between 'B' and the corresponding \bar{n}_A values was plotted (Fig. 1). From this curve, the value of practical pK_{OH}^H was determined corresponding to B value at \bar{n}_A equal to 0.5.

A plot of $\log \frac{\bar{n}_A}{1-\bar{n}_A}$ against B was also drawn.

From this curve, the value of practical pK_{OH}^H was obtained. The two values agree quite well (Fig. 2).

Fig. 1. 2-Hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde-thiosemicarbazone formation curve.

From the titration curves of solutions (ii) and (iii), \bar{n} and pL values were calculated. The \bar{n} values were plotted against the corresponding pL values to get

Fig. 2. 2-Hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde-thiosemicarbazone the formation curves of the metal complex equilibrium (Fig. 3). From these formation curves, the

Fig. 3. Metal-Ligand systems of 2-Hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde-thiosemicarbazone Formation curves.

values of stepwise stability constants, $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ were computed which correspond to pL values at $\bar{n} = 0.5$ and 1.5 respectively. In addition, the least square method was used to calculate $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ in the case of Ni, Zn, Cu and Co systems. The most representative values have been recorded in the Table 1.

TABLE 1—STEPWISE STABILITY CONSTANTS OF VARIOUS COMPLEXES

Metal ion	H ⁺	Cu ²⁺	Ni ²⁺	Co ²⁺	Zn ²⁺	Cd ²⁺	Mg ²⁺
$\log K_1$	9.80	10.33	9.45	9.88	7.90	7.13	3.27
$\log K_2$	—	8.27	8.70	8.92	6.22	—	—

The order of stability of bivalent metal chelates was $\text{Cu}^{2+} > \text{Co}^{2+} > \text{Ni}^{2+} > \text{Zn}^{2+} > \text{Cd}^{2+} > \text{Mg}^{2+}$.

The reversal of the order in the case of cobalt and nickel complexes as compared to that observed by Maley and Mellor⁶ may be attributed to the closeness of the values in the present investigation.

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